

Classical Average Energy Conservation in Quantum Bound State

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Physically, momentum p is related to an experimentally measurable impulse hit. Kinetic energy, on the other hand, is not directly measured through a hit with a target. This begs the question of how kinetic energy and energy conservation arises. We first consider this question by focusing on the scalar nature of kinetic energy and argue that attempting to create conservation equations for p momentum, even in one dimension, lead to problems due to the sign of p , i.e. there time reversal invariance issues. If one has a conservation law of the form $p(x_1)+V(x_1) = p(x_2)+V(x_2)$ and $V(x)$ is supposed to represent the impulse hits (in a kind of stationary manner) then $p_1(x_1), p_2(x_2)$ could be positive or negative which breaks the conservation equation. For example, a particle with positive $p(x_1)$ may move to x_2 such that $p(x_2)$ is positive. On the other hand, a $p(x_1)$ positive may move beyond x_2 to a point where velocity becomes zero and then reverse its motion arriving at x_2 with $-p(x_2)$. As a result, a different conservation scheme is needed and we suggest that this leads to the introduction of kinetic energy.

As a second part of the note, we consider the quantum mechanical free particle $\exp(ipx)$. It has a precise p and $pp/2m$ just like a classical particle, but also a wavelength \hbar/p suggesting uncertainty in position. This allows for two slit interference patterns to occur, but there is no violation of conservation of energy, or conservation of momentum. One just has to deal with probabilistic interference. Thus, we suggest that even with quantum mechanics, there must be a conservation of energy equation of the form: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$. The question then becomes: How does one form $KE_{ave}(x)$? The form $\exp(ipx)$ (a kind of probability) governs the position of the particle (which is linked with its physical p related to an impulse hit), so we suggest that $pp/2m$ (kinetic energy) be treated in the same manner. For example, a particle with momentum p has x uncertainty, so it may interact with one slit or another in a 2-slit apparatus with slit spacing of \hbar/p , but a p impulse hit still occurs and conservation of energy still applies. We use the example of one dimensional reflection/refraction to argue for the form of average momentum and then generalize to kinetic energy.

Momentum or Energy in a Conservation Equation?

We wish to consider the following scenario. Consider a particle with momentum p_1 moving to the right in one dimension. It enters x_1 at t_1 with p_1 , undergoes some stochastic impulse hits and emerges at x_2 at t_2 with momentum p_2 which is also positive. This situation is repeatable and always yields the same p_1, x_1, t_1 and p_2, x_2, t_2 values.

If there is time reversal symmetry, which should exist, one could consider the time reversed scenario. At this point, only momentum is considered because it is physically measurable through an impulse hit in the classical world. (In the quantum world, there is a second measurement related to interference, e.g. spatial resolution as in the 2-slit mechanism.)

Kinetic energy (nonrelativistic), on the other hand, does not seem to be so physical, which begs the question: Why is it used?

We first try to create a conservation law using only momentum and consider only the case of a particle which has positive p_1 at x_1, t_1 and positive p_2 at x_2, t_2 . We suggest thinking in terms of: $dp(x)/dx$ or $dp(t)/dt$ which have the same sign for all x, t , i.e. p is continuously decreasing from x_1 to x_2 . One may then write: $dp/dx = F_1(x)$ and $dp/dt = F_2(t)$, where F_1 and F_2 are math functions. Then: $\Delta p = \int F_1(x) dx$ and $\Delta p = \int F_2(t) dt$. If one has: $F_1(x) = dV_1/dx$ and $F_2 = dV_2/dt$, one has two conservation laws: $p(x_1) + V_1(x_1) = p(x_2) + V_2(x_2)$ ((1a)) and $p(t_1) + V_2(t_1) = p(t_2) + V_2(t_2)$ ((1b))

((1a)) and ((1b)), however, have serious problems. If one considers time reversal, then $p(x_1) \rightarrow -p(x_1)$ and $p(x_2) \rightarrow -p(x_2)$ and neither ((1a)) nor ((1b)). One would have to change the sign of V_1 and V_2 , but these are supposed to represent a condition in space.

There exists a second problem. A particle with $p(x_1)$ may travel to x_2 and have $p(x_2)$, with p being positive at both x_1 and x_2 . Alternatively, $p(x_1)$ may travel to x_3 , reach a velocity of 0, turn around and move backwards reaching x_2 with $p(x_2)$ in the opposite direction. Thus, there seems to be a problem with ((1a)) and ((1b)) because these distinguish the sign of p . $p(x_1) - p(x_2)$ does not have the same value in the two scenarios, but one wishes $V_1(x)$ and $V_2(t)$ to be stationary properties and not have to change their signs as well.

It seems that if one wishes to have stationary quantities representing the impulse region, one needs to have a scheme which does not distinguish between forwards and backwards motion. This, we argue, is the motivation for developing conservation of energy when the physical quantity (experimental measurable) seems to be momentum p due to impulse.

As a result, one may use $dp = F_2(t)dt$ with $p = mv$ and $dx = vdt$ in a tiny interval to obtain: $\int p/m dp = \int F_2(t)dt$, as done in Newtonian mechanics. This leads to a quantity $pp/2m$ which does not depend on the sign of p . In the three dimensional case, it becomes a dot product, i.e. a scalar, so one may develop a scalar conservation of energy equation as is also done in Newtonian mechanics. The two problematic scenarios in the momentum case are no longer problematic in the energy conservation picture. This means that a free particle, one which is not interacting, still has special property called kinetic energy given by $pp/2m$ nonrelativistically. Thus:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Quantum Mechanics

We belabour this point because a quantum free particle is also described by a precise momentum p value which corresponds to a physical impulse hit. In other words, a quantum free particle, or even photon, renders an impulse hit as if it were classical. The difference is that a quantum free particle carries a built-in resolution of time and space, i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ where $E = pp/2m$ nonrelativistically. One no longer has a particle which acts like a point. If there are two slits separated by about a wavelength \hbar/p , the particle has a precise momentum, but uncertainty in position, and might react (undergo) an impulse hit with one or the other of the slits. This leads to an ADD or OR probability situation because there was uncertainty in position to begin with, even though p is precise.

We argue, however, that concepts of conservation of momentum and energy do not disappear for a quantum particle. p momentum and $pp/2m$ exist for a quantum free particle. Momentum must still be conserved whether there is spatial resolution or not. We also suggest that average kinetic energy should be conserved too if there is a potential $V(x)$. We argue for this because, if one uses $\exp(ipx)$ as a kind of probability, one should use this same probability to describe average values of functions of p . Thus, in the case of interference from a 2-slit mechanism, one has:

$$\exp(i p_1 \cdot r) + \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) \quad \text{where } p_1 \text{ and } p_2 \text{ have the same magnitude ((3))}$$

Spatial resolution allows for two different impulse hits, one from one slit and one from the other, but the situation is probabilistic. If a collision occurs from slit one, momentum is p_1 (vector), while for slit 2 it is p_2 (vector). It seems one should use $\exp(i p_1 \cdot r)$ and $\exp(i p_2 \cdot r)$ as relative probability weights. If this is the case, there is no reason not to extend this idea to $pp/2m$, nonrelativistic kinetic energy.

One may note that ((3)) includes a special condition, namely that p_1 and p_2 have the same magnitude. In a more general case, even the magnitude of p could change. For example, one could have a one dimensional problem with an average $V(x)$ causing impulse hits as described in the first section. $V(x)$ is a smooth function which approximates the stochastic impulse hits which occur. In such a case, one has an OR situation which all possible p values (one dimensional) or:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{where } a(p) \text{ is a weight ((4))}$$

Again average p and average kinetic energy, normalized, may be expressed as:

$$\langle p \rangle = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p \ exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad \langle pp/2m \rangle = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \ exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((5))$$

If the above is not convincing, one may consider the problem of one dimensional reflection/refraction for either a photon (n_1, n_2 , motion in x direction, interface along y axis) or the analogous particle problem (constant V_1 for $x < 0$, constant V_2 for $x > 0$). In both cases, energy is constant for all x . In such a case, one writes a continuity equation for $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative, i.e. for the photon case:

$$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad \text{where } p_1 = pn_1 \text{ and } p_2 = pn_2 \quad ((6a))$$

$$p_1 A \exp(ip_1 x) - p_1 B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((6b))$$

Even though ((6b)) has the form of continuity of the first derivative, dividing ((6b)) by ((6a)) represents equating average momentum at $x=0$. Thus, this problem seems to verify the use of $\exp(ipx)$ s as weights in calculating average p , and hence $pp/2m$ we argue.

The Case for Conservation of Average Energy in a Quantum Single Particle Bound State

From Newtonian mechanics and experiment, one knows that momentum is conserved, in the quantum world where one still uses precise momentum values as in $\exp(ipx)$. Momentum still has the same physical meaning even though $\exp(ipx)$ indicates a probabilistic resolution in space which allows for multiple impulse hits which must be treated probabilistically, i.e. interfere. In section 1, we argued for establishing a conservation of energy law (using the concept of kinetic energy) because one required a scalar quantity which is time reversal invariant. The problem in section 1, however, is based on physical impulse hits which still occur in quantum mechanics. Kinetic energy and conservation are only introduced as a way to analyze these impulse hits which lead to repeatable observations.

As a result, we suggest that even in a quantum bound state, one must have conservation of average energy. It is known that $V(x)$ may create different p values and that these are associated with regions of space (of the order of \hbar/p the wavelength) and are not points as in classical mechanics. This leads to interference, but one may still calculate an average kinetic energy using the $\exp(ipx)$ weights i.e.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((7))$$

The fact that $\exp(ipx)$ appears in ((7)) means that physically one may knock out the particle and it will have a momentum p with a probability weight somehow linked to $a(p)$. The spatial resolution of a particle $\exp(ipx)$, however, leads to spatial patterns and in the case of multiple p 's, one has spatial patterns which may lead to an average $KE(x)$ at x . It seems that there is no problem dealing with the concept of an average kinetic energy as $V(x)$ itself was considered in section 1 (a section on classical physics) as being an average which describes a stochastic hit scenario which yields repeatable results.

Thus, we argue for:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is, in fact, the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

In the quantum case, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with spatial resolution which is a way of measuring p , i.e. the translational generator multiplied by $-i$ yields p : $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. The kinetic energy of a free particle is also associated with resolution in space. There is an average kinetic energy linked with resolution in space with no interaction. If one multiplies ((8)) by $W(x)$, then $V(x)W(x)$ represents Maxwell-Boltzmann like interactions at x points, i.e. $\exp(ikx) \exp(ipx)$ where $V(x) = \text{sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$. The resolution probability $\exp(ipx)$ is orthonormal to other $\exp(ip_1x)$ s and this allows one to have ((8)) which applies to the full bound single particle state as well as the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ which is associated with a particle in a constant effective potential:

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, it is not only the full single particle probability $W(x)$ which is associated with conservation of energy (as in ((8))), but also each possible free particle which may be knocked out from any x as in ((9)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first try to consider why the concept of kinetic energy is developed when p momentum is associated with a physical impulse. We argue that kinetic energy is needed to establish a conservation law which is time reversal invariant. In order to describe a particle with momentum p_1 at x_1, t_1 moving through a one dimensional region of impulse hits and emerging with p_2 at x_2, t_2 , one needs to create a scalar $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ such that $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$, i.e. a conservation law exists. We argue that time reversal issues do not allow one to establish such a law using p only because p becomes $-p$ upon time reversal.

We next consider the quantum mechanical case of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$. In such a situation there is a probabilistic spatial resolution, but p is precise and should follow classical rules. I.e. conservation of momentum should still exist as should some kind of average conservation of kinetic energy. We argue that $V(x)$ is a smooth average function describing impulse hits even in the classical case, so there should be no issue with having $KE(x)$ being an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s in the quantum situation. We also try to give a reason why one may create $KE_{ave}(x)$ using $\exp(ipx)$ s as weights, by considering the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem.